

Standard Enthalpy of Formation of Bismuthyl Nitrate

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At room temperature, bismuth dissolves in fairly concentrated nitric acid solutions ($>6M$ - HNO_3) liberating NO gas. The acid solution on evaporation produces a white residue which on drying yields anhydrous crystals of bismuthyl nitrate, $BiONO_3(c)$. The standard enthalpy of formation of $BiONO_3(c)$ has not been reported even in recent compilations¹⁻³.

We report in this work the enthalpies of solution of bismuth metal, bismuthyl nitrate, nitric acid and water in their standard states in $11M$ - HNO_3 solution. From the enthalpies of solution, ΔH_{soln} , the standard enthalpy of formation of bismuthyl nitrate can be calculated by eqns. (1) and (2).

$$\Delta H_f^\circ BiONO_3(c) = 2\Delta H_f^\circ HNO_3(l) - \Delta H_f^\circ H_2O(l) - \Delta H_f^\circ NO(g) + \Delta H \quad \dots (1)$$

where

$$\Delta H = \Delta H_{soln} Bi(c) - \Delta H_{soln} BiONO_3(c) + 2\Delta H_{soln} HNO_3(l) - \Delta H_{soln} H_2O(l) \quad \dots (2)$$

Experimental

Pure bismuth metal (99.999%) was obtained from Nuclear Fuel Complex, Hyderabad (India). It was finely cut and sealed in fragile bulbs under dry nitrogen gas⁴. Bismuthyl nitrate was obtained by dissolving the pure metal in $11M$ - HNO_3 and the resulting solution evaporated to dryness and finally baked at 115° for several hours. The compound was analysed for bismuth and nitrogen (Found: Bi, 71.2; N, 4.9; Calc. for $BiONO_3(c)$: Bi, 72.8; N, 4.9%). The white crystalline compound was sealed in fragile bulbs as above. On strongly heating a weighed sample of $BiONO_3(c)$, the loss in weight corresponded with the formation of a yellowish-white residue of Bi_2O_3 from $BiONO_3(c)$. BDH 'AnalaR' nitric acid ($\approx 95\%$) was used without further concentration.

A closed-system calorimeter described earlier⁵ was used. Briefly, it consists of a 200 ml 'pyrex' silvered Dewar vessel with an attachment of a water-tight perspex lid. A number of accessories like a temperature sensor ($10K\Omega$ -thermistor), a calibration heater (manganin heater), a mercury-seal stirrer, a

fragile ampoule holder, an ampoule breaker, and B_7 coned inlet and outlet tubes were provided, all of which passed through the grooves cut across the transparent lid and held in fixed positions by vacuum O-rings sandwiched between the perspex sheets of the lid. The calorimeter was immersed completely in a thermostated water bath at $298 \pm 0.1K$. All measurements were made under an atmosphere of dry nitrogen.

TABLE II—ENTHALPIES OF SOLUTION OF SUBSTANCES IN $11M$ - HNO_3 AT $298 K$

Substances	Weight (gms)	Concn. (mole/l)	H_{soln} kJ mole ⁻¹	Mean
Bi(c)	0.0522	0.0014	-267.8	-277.5 $\pm$ 10.0
	0.0560	0.0015	-286.6	
	0.0632	0.0017	-278.2	
$BiONO_3(c)$	0.2182	0.0043	-27.2	-28.9 $\pm$ 2.0
	0.3077	0.0061	-29.2	
	0.3760	0.0074	-29.9	
$HNO_3(l)$	1.66299	0.1508	-11.2	-11.4 $\pm$ 0.3
	1.68316	0.1527	-11.6	
$H_2O(l)$	0.99883	0.3171	-1.9	-1.9 $\pm$ 0.2
	1.56625	0.4972	-1.8	
	1.92044	0.6097	-2.1	

Results and Discussion

Table I lists the enthalpies of solution of $Bi(c)$, $BiONO_3(c)$, $HNO_3(l)$ and $H_2O(l)$ in $11M$ - HNO_3 solution. No correction for the loss of heat of the calorimetric liquid due to the escape of evolved NO gas in the dissolution of bismuth metal has been made. However, it will have a minimal effect on the enthalpy of solution considering the limits of experimental uncertainty. Substituting the values of ΔH_{soln} from the table in eqn. (2) we get $\Delta H = -269.5$ kJ mole⁻¹. The standard enthalpies of formation of $H_2O(l)$, $HNO_3(l)$ and $NO(g)$ are -285.8, -174.1 and +90.2 kJ mole⁻¹ respectively¹. On utilization of the above data in eqn. (1) we get $\Delta H_f^\circ BiONO_3(c) = -422.0 \pm 10$ kJ mol⁻¹. The average error has been estimated as twice the standard mean deviation.

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